

Research Article

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Awareness and Usage of Innovative Video-Assisted Application among Adult Literacy Learners in Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study explores the awareness and usage of Innovative Video Assisted Application (IVAA) among adult literacy learners in Ondo State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was employed, utilizing two research questions and one hypothesis. The sample consisted of 95 adult literacy learners, selected from three literacy centers across the Ondo State senatorial districts. Data was collected using a self-developed questionnaire, validated by experts in education and language. Reliability was established with Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of 0.79 and 0.80 for awareness and usage, respectively. Statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation, and t-test were used to analyze the data. Results indicated a high level of awareness and usage of IVAA among adult literacy learners, with no significant gender-based differences in usage for learning cultural literacy ($t = .666$; $p > 0.05$). The study recommends that workshops be organized for instructors and learners to enhance the effective use of IVAA in literacy programs. This underscores the potential of video-assisted applications to enhance adult education and foster cultural literacy.

Keywords

Information and Communication Technologies, Innovative Video Assisted Application, Adult literacy learners, Cultural literacy, Awareness, Usage.

1. Introduction

The development of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in education and media combination requires media literacy skills developed through innovative teaching and learning methods. Technological tools, communication technologies and participatory media are incorporated in formal and informal education, Curricula and their effectiveness and acceptance

in the teaching and learning process is a subject for research (Turan & Cetintas, 2020).

Videos are important window that can accommodate and expose the minds and hearts of learners on current educational development. This is because education has been seen as instrument of change and national development (Edem & Ekon, 2021) Video is also known as the recorded

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moving images that could appeal to the sense of sight and videos can assist students understand the course content and offer them the golden opportunity to actively involved effectively in a stimulating contemporary learning environment. (Galatsopoulou et al., 2022).

According to Tayade et al., (2018) video play significant role in teaching and learning when it is used effectively, it stimulates interest among the learners and induces longer retention of factual ideas as the learners come into contact with what is being taught. Ferraro et al., (2021) revealed that people remember 10% of what they read 20% of what they hear, 30% of what they see, 50% of what they hear and see, 70% of what they say and 90% of what they say as they do a thing. Also, Benedict, (2014), deduced that: I hear; I forget, I see; I remember, I do, I understand therefore, the above illustration confirmed that video has to do with hearing and seeing and it could be recommends that video-assisted instruction becomes powerful tools in socializing effects on students, an indeed, brings more interactive learning into the crowded classroom (Abraga & Hambre, 2017). Mustofa et al., (2022) surveyed the acceptance of economics learning media through movie clips and studies perceived ease of use (PEU), perceived usefulness (PU), attitude toward using (ATU), and behavioural intention to use (BIU). From their study a significant relationship was discovered by them. Gatatsopoulou et al., (2022) revealed that students' positive attitude towards video can be used in multiple active learning scenarios to enhance their motivation and engagement level and provide a learning environment that is joyful, collaborative and welcoming. Songkram and Osuwan, (2022) stated that videos have good content such as visuals, text and audio can be shared on different online communities. Furthermore, videos can be interlinked with resource links discussion boards, online chat of a distance learning environment (Mayer et al., 2020).

The concept of adult connotes different

meaning to researchers and the most universally accepted criterion used in defining adult is the age. According to Mbava et al., (2014), people, who are 15 years or older can participate in Adult Basic Education and Training. In Nigeria, eighteen years and above is the legal age of an adult. This study's criterion does not based on age limit. It is expected that before attaining eighteen years, that individual must have gone through both primary and secondary school respectively. There are those who due to poverty or other misfortunes were left out of the formal education system and want to catch up with privilege ones. The type of education they now engage is out of school type. It is assumed that an out of school education is meant for adults. Therefore, any individual found in literally programme meant for adults is therefore considered as an adult (Mbaval et al., 2014). Nwafor and Agi, (2013), opined that adult literacy programme that would ensure functionality has the following component. Reading, writing, Mathematics, English as a second or other language (ESOL) and cultural literacy. The cultural literacy is the ability to understand and appreciate the similarities and differences in the customs, values and beliefs of one's own culture and the cultures of others (World Bank Report, 2010). Awareness is one of the factors that affect the use of videos in teaching and learning process. Opeke and Odunlade (2011) described awareness as an understanding of presence of a phenomenon. Also, Alharthi (2016) sees awareness as a knowledge of something which survives or comprehension of a particular situation based on happening or information. Edem aui9 Ekon, (2021) posits that vast majority (87.5%) of students were aware of video clips tool that aids learning only a few (12.5%) indicated their non-awareness of video clips for teaching and learning in Nigeria universities. Ayelaagbe, (2019) investigated the assessment of the mobile phone-based literacy programme as a functional basic strategy among, adult learners and it was revealed that adult learners have average level of awareness on the use of

mobile phone-based instructional literacy programme for learning. In a study carried out by Nwaizugbu and Atuzie (2023) on awareness and usage of innovative educational hypermedia among Rivers State Universities. It was affirmed that students in Rivers State University have a low awareness and usage level when it comes to mobile applications that can improve academic performance and students use social/entertainment mobile applications than they use academic oriented application software. Also, Gaffar & Kumar (2019), who in their study sort to find out the awareness, access and usage of mobile applications among the users of a technical institute library in Rourkela include 35% of the respondent are aware of mobile application available in the library, 11% of the respondents are using mobile application of the library, 31% of the respondents are using smart phones for educational and library, social media, e-mails and gaming purpose, 13% of the respondents are accessing available library resources/e-journals on their smart phone, 31% of the respondents have download 6-10 applications on their mobile device.

Recently, teaching has moved from the traditional instructional approach to video supported instructions. Many instructional organizations are accommodating classrooms with videos supported learning and schooling has been showing its relevance in education. The videos can be used in many ways in order to make an impact in teaching and learning. Ozdamli and Ozdal (2018) opined those videos encourages instructors to consider it for flipped classroom approach, where students can study the instructional materials at their own rate and afterward learn the detail more greatly in the class time.

Also, instructional videos can easy practical learning by providing with basic steps and ways on how to go with the actual practical package, and how to examine it in an accident-free environment As a result, it enables learners to obtain the skills in organizing and conducting practical in an effective way. Videos can be helpful as

instructor in representing the process or interactive facts in order to help in mastery of studying where learners can see convoluted mechanical or clinical procedures many times when they are needed. Furthermore, the modern web-based media players do have interactive features that can be employed in order to increase active learning methods with learners. Videos based instructional contents provide learners with producing opportunity of authentic learning and also how academics from the research-based view and advocacy can be motivated by instructional videos (Bawa et al., 2019). Instructional videos enable learners acquire information about the course whenever they want and learners can be provided with everlasting to all the instructional materials by simply uploading video lectures through the Learning Management System (LMS) or websites. Instructional video can make a considerable effect in a short period and it enables the learners to stop, rewind, pause and then manipulate the timeline of study (Beheshti et al. 2018). Galatsopoulou et al. (2022) carried out a study on the use of video-based assisted active learning and it was revealed from the study that videos can be used in multiple active learning scenarios to enhance students' motivation and engagement and provide joyful, collaborative, and hospitable learning environment videos are widely used in asynchronous self-paced and autonomous learning. They are used in formal education but also for informal education and training.

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) utilise a linear simple course structure and the course content is presented through short video lectures (Birgili & Demir, 2021), in their study, refers to low-quality YouTube videos that are not always truthful or relevant and may affect learning. Students also who do not own gadgets, a laptop, or a portable tool may find it difficult to benefit from self-paced video-based education. (Sabolic et al., 2021).

Gender is one of the key learner factors which may affect learners' awareness and the use of

innovative video Assisted Application. There are divergent views on the gender issues concerning the use technology in teaching and learning process. Bollinger and Supanakom (2011) showed that females and males differ in the overall functions of using technology. This makes it more challenging to explore the awareness and usage of females and males towards Innovative Video Assisted Application when applying multimedia into classroom discussion to assist adult literacy learners. Wang and Hung (2022) in their study revealed that female students and male students perceived media classroom significantly different in their learning on media classroom communication. It was also revealed from their study that female students perceived that in media classroom they are more likely to be blended, to be task-oriented to be self-adaptive and to be self-esteem in their learning. Nwagbo and Ugwanyi (2015) revealed that a number of extent studies evidenced that ICT – related differences between female and males lessened mainly in the access to ICT and basic computer skills. Shedrack and Robert (2016) opined those students taught Physics practical with video-taped instruction performed better than their counterparts in the conventional group. Certain investigations revealed that gender differences do not exist. Alkhasawneh and Alarazy (2015) find no significant gender-based differences among the staff. They believe that this is due to ICT use having become integrated in today's world. Also, Bhat & Bashir (2017) revealed that no significant differences between male and female university teachers with respect to gender, and that males and females have a such as attitude to ICT -use. Similarly, Soyda let al. (2012) analysed academic staff at a Turkish University and revealed that gender is mostly not a factor in e-learning readiness. Hence, this study seeks to investigate the assessment of awareness and usage of innovative Video Assisted Application (IVAA) among adult learners in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Video-based educational contents are cue to enhancing literary for both applaud awareness and educating the masses in formal, non-formal and informal learning domain. Educational videos have unique features such as round-the-clock availability, accessibility from any location, formally complied contents and up-to-date materials which provide immense relevance to the students and teachers and contribute crucially to improving student engagement in classroom activities. The traditional face-to-face learning framework or a typical classroom environment is attributed by more interactive and discussion-based learning settings, whereas, educational videos enable learning through reflection which, otherwise would be hard to achieve in traditional teaching process. A lot of research has been conducted to investigate the awareness and usage of innovative Video Assisted Application in schools but non- to the researcher's knowledge has empirically determined the awareness and usage of adult literacy learners in Ondo State, Nigeria. Therefore, the problem of this study is the adult literacy Video Assisted Application for learning cultural literacy in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

- (1) investigate the awareness level of adult literacy learners on the usage of innovative Video Assisted Application learners for learning cultural literacy.
- (2) access the level of usage of innovative Video Assisted Application for learning cultural literacy by adult literacy learners.
- (3) find out the impact of gender on the use of innovative Video Assisted Application for learning cultural literacy by adult learners.

Research Questions

In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the following research questions were raised and answered.

- (1) What is the awareness level of adult learners on the usage of innovative Video Assisted Application for learning cultural literacy?
- (2) What is the level of usage of innovation video assisted application for learning cultural literacy by adult learners?

Research Hypothesis

The following research hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the adult learners' usage of innovative Video Assisted Application for learning Cultural literacy based on gender.

2. Methods

This study used a quantitative research design based on a survey method through questionnaire. Survey was employed on this research study, because it is an efficient way for collecting information from a large number of respondents. The sampling techniques used for this study were purposive and simple random sampling techniques and the population consisted of all adult literacy learners from all adult literacy centres in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Simple random technique was used to select three (3) adult literacy centres from Ondo State. One adult literacy centre was selected from each senatorial district (Ondo Central, North and South). Purposive sampling was used to select the respondents because all the adult literacy centres in Ondo State used the same curriculum and same mode of receiving instructions.

In order to give all the respondents an equal opportunity for been selected purposive sampling was used to select ninety five (95) adult literacy learners. From Ondo Central district thirty four (34) respondents were selected from adult literacy centre and twenty (20) were females while fourteen (14) were

males. From Ondo South senatorial district, thirty six (36) respondents were selected, nineteen (19) were females and seventeen (17) were males. Also, from Ondo North senatorial district, twenty five (25) respondents were selected. Fifteen (15) were female while ten (10) were males respectively.

The main instrument for the study is researchers designed questionnaire titled "Awareness and Usage of Innovation Video Assisted Application among Adult literacy learners' questionnaires (AUIVAAALLQ)". The questionnaire was written in English language and was translated to Yoruba language for the better understanding of Adult literacy learners. The questionnaire consists of two (2) sections; Section "A" demographic data of the respondents and section "B" contains items on the Adult literacy learners' awareness and usage of Innovative Video Assisted Application (IVAA) for learning cultural literacy. The instrument was on a 4-point scale of Strongly Disagree (SD), Disagree (D), Agree (A), and Strongly Agree (SA). The questionnaire was exposed to both face and content validity to check the appropriateness and adequacy of the content of the instrument. The English version of the instrument was given to an English language expert, the Yoruba version was given to Yoruba expert and one (1) expert from Department of Educational Technology, Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo, Nigeria. Their advice and suggestions were used to adjust the questionnaire to produce a final draft.

The questionnaire was tested for reliability on twenty (20) randomly selected adult literacy learners from adult literacy centres in Yewa South Local Government adult literacy centres in Ogun State, who were not part of this study. The data gathered from the trial test study was analysed to check for internal consistency in reliability and Cronbach Alpha value of 0.79 on awareness and 0.80 on the usage of Innovative Video assisted application for learning cultural literacy among adult learners. This

indicated that the research instrument was highly reliable.

The researcher visited the adult literacy centres selected for the study with the help of adult literacy instructor to administer copies of the questionnaire to the respondents involved. The researcher read the versions of the questionnaire to the respondents for

better understanding and through guidance the adult literacy learners were able to fill the questionnaire. At the end of this exercise, ninety five (95) valid copies of the questionnaire were retrieved from the respondents upon which analysis of the result were carried out using, mean, standard deviation and t-test to answer the research questions raised and to test the hypothesis formulated for the study.

3. Result and Discussion

Results

Research Question1: What is the awareness level of adult learners on utilization of innovative video application for learning cultural literacy?

Table 1

Adult Learners' Awareness of Utilization of Innovative Video Application for Teaching and Learning

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D
<i>I am aware that usage of Innovative Video Assisted application can:</i>						
Improve my academic performance.	42	34	19	0	3.24	.77
Make me learn better	31	58	6	0	3.26	.57
Increase my productivity as adult learners	0	8	40	47	1.59	.64
Meet my learning needs	22	60	13	0	3.09	.60
Save my time	43	23	21	8	3.06	1.00
Help to associate with daily life	11	15	23	46	1.91	1.05
Use in the learning	17	64	14	0	3.03	.57
Enable me gain more knowledge	0	31	43	21	2.11	.74
Provide flexibility in interaction	2	16	54	23	1.97	.71
Improve the quality of my understanding of subject of the lesson.	3	13	35	44	1.74	.81
Weighted Average					2.50	

Key; *SD* = Strongly Disagree, *D* = Disagree, *A* = Agree, *SA* = Strongly Agree

Decision Value: *Low*=0.00-2.44, *High* = 2.45-4.00

Table 1 shows the level of awareness of adult learners on utilization of innovative video application for learning cultural literacy. The table shows that the adult learners are aware that innovative video assisted application can: improve their academic performance ($\bar{x} = 3.24$), make them learn better ($\bar{x} = 3.26$), meet their learning needs ($\bar{x} = 3.09$), saves their time ($\bar{x} = 3.06$), and use in learning ($\bar{x} = 3.03$). The table also shows that the adult learners are not aware of the following: increase their productivity as adult learners (\bar{x}

= 1.59), help to associate with daily life ($\bar{x} = 1.91$), enable me gain more knowledge ($\bar{x} = 2.11$), provide flexibility in interaction ($\bar{x} = 1.97$), and improve the quality of understanding of the subject of the lesson ($\bar{x} = 1.74$). Meanwhile, based on the value of the weighted average (2.50 out of 4.00 maximum value obtainable) which falls, within the decision value for **high**, it can be inferred that the awareness level of adult learners on utilization of innovative video application for learning cultural literacy is high.

Research Question2: What is the level of utilization of innovative video assisted application for learning cultural literacy by adult learners?

Table 2

Level of Utilisation of Innovative Video Assisted Application

Item	S	A	D	S	Me	Std.
	A			D	an	D
Innovative Video Assisted Application (IVAA) clears the concepts of cultural literacy	5 2	2 8	1 5	0 8	3.3	.75
IVAA improves my performance in adult literacy class	2 7	5 2	6 1	1 9	2.9	.91
IVAA prevents boredom and address all the senses	2 8	3 3	2 3	1 1	2.8	.99
It enables me to recall the new knowledge	4 6	3 3	1 6	0 2	3.3	.75
Using IVAA makes learning more interactive and livelier	1 4	7 0	1 1	0 3	3.0	.51
IVAA enables me concentrate in the classroom	4 0	2 6	2 9	0 2	3.1	.85
Using IVAA increases my participation during the class	3 6	2 6	2 6	7 6	2.9	.98
IVAA supports learning with aspects from real life	4 4	3 0	1 4	7 7	3.1	.94
IVAA is good for demonstrating cultural literacy	3 0	6 0	3 0	2 4	3.2	.61
Using IVAA makes literacy lesson more enjoyable and interesting.	3 8	4 9	8 9	0 2	3.3	.62
Weighted Average					3.14	

Key; *SD* = Strongly Disagree, *D* = Disagree, *A* = Agree, *SA* = Strongly Agree

Decision Value: *Low*=0.00-2.44, *High* = 2.45-4.00

Table 2 shows the level of utilization of innovative video assisted application for learning cultural literacy by adult learners. The table indicates agreement among the students for all items with, "Innovative Video Assisted Application (IVAA) clears the concepts of cultural literacy" received the highest mean score ($\bar{x} = 3.38$), while "IVAA prevents boredom and address all the senses" had the lowest mean score ($\bar{x} = 2.82$). Meanwhile, based on the value of the weighted average (3.14 out of 4.00 maximum value obtainable) which

falls, within the decision value for **high**, it can be inferred that the level of utilization of innovative video assisted application for learning cultural literacy by adult learners is high.

Hypotheses Testing

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the adult learners' utilization of Innovative Video Assisted Application for learning cultural literacy based on gender.

Table 3:

Summary of T-test Showing Difference in Male and Female Adult Learners' Utilization of Innovative Video Assisted Application for Learning Cultural Literacy

Grouping Variable (Gender)	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	T	Sig	Remark
Male	43	31.5	3.03	93	.666	.507	Not Significant
Female	52	31.1	2.60				

Table 3 shows the difference in the utilization of Innovative Video Assisted Application for learning cultural literacy by male and female adult learners. The table shows that the mean score for male adult learners is 31.56 while that of female adult learners is 31.17. The mean values showed no appreciable difference. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the adult learners' utilization of Innovative Video Assisted Application for learning cultural literacy based on gender ($df = 93$; $t = .666$; $p > 0.05$). Hence, hypothesis 1 is retained.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined the awareness and usage of innovative video assisted application among adult literacy learners. It was revealed that awareness level of adult literacy learners on the usage of innovative video assisted application for learning cultural literacy is high. This finding is aligned with results of previous studies (Nwazugbu & Atuzie 2023, Gaffar & Kumar, 2019, Ayelaagbe, 2019 and Edem & Ekon, 2021) who revealed that students were aware of the usage of innovative technology in teaching - learning process.

The research question two (2) of this study revealed the level of usage of innovative video assisted application among adult literacy learners for learning cultural literacy is high. This agrees

with the findings of Ozdamti and Ozdal, 2018, Beheshiet al., 2018, Galatsopoulou et al., 2022 and Birgili and Demiri, 2021 who found out that Innovative Video Assisted Application (IVAA) can be used in multiple active learning scenarios to enhance students' motivation and engagement and provide a joyful, collaborative and hospitable learning environment but, Pattier (2021) and Sublic et al., 2021 differs in their views that learners found it difficult to benefit from self-paced video-based education.

Moderating effect of gender (male and female) was also studied in this study. Hypothesis 1 revealed that there was no significant difference in adult literacy learners' usage of innovative video assisted application for learning cultural literacy based on gender. This agreed with the findings of Bollinger and Ugwanyi, 2015. Bhat and Bashir, 2017, but the finding contradicts the

findings of Soydal et al., (2012) that gender is mostly not a factor in e-learning readiness.

5. Conclusions

From the findings of this study, the following conclusion were made: - The awareness level of adult literacy learners on the usage of Innovative Video Assisted Application (IVAA) was high; also it was revealed that adult literacy learners usage of IVAA for learning cultural literacy was high. It was revealed that there is no significant difference in the adult literacy learner's usage of innovative video assisted application for learning cultural literacy based on gender. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations have been made:

Ministry of adult literacy should organize

periodic workshops to build the capacity of the adult instructors to effectively incorporate innovative video assisted application to their lessons to improve learning outcomes of adult literacy leanings, government of Ondo State in partnership with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and other private sector organizations should design and implement interventions to deals with barriers to effective implementation of innovative video assisted application in teaching and learning to improve quality education of adult literacy learners , and adult literacy learners should be well trained on the use of innovative video assisted application for learning cultural literacy and they should be provided with enough laptops, computers and relevant digital materials to support IVAA in teaching and learning process.

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